

B r i F a c e

H2020:MSCA-IF-2018

Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

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Industrial partners & Stakeholders: Sika A.G., Denco Structural Eng. P.C.

Duration:24 months (start date: June 2019) | Overall budget: € 212 933,76

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223811/factsheet/en>

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D1: Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Assessment of existing data

Having searched the key databases for Civil Engineering, material science and infrastructure (Scopus, Google Scholar etc.) the Principal investigator (PI) noted that the existing literature overlooks to the questions this research is interested in looking at (interface efficiency of reinforced concrete bridge decks retrofitted with fiber reinforced polymer schemes-FRP). Furthermore, there is not a dataset that the PI could benefit from to carry out the research. Therefore, it is a must that the PI collects original data by conducting simulations (e.g. finite element models using Ansys Mechanical software), experiments, surveys from retrofitted bridges in Europe form data collected and provided by the industrial partners of the project, to answer the question of this research.

Information on new data

The outcome of the analysis and tests will be original and new data. The first set of data will be collected through simulations using finite element analyses and will be produced by running input text files (.txt extension).

The second set of data will be collected through tests in the lab (double lap tests, exposure due to corrosion and/or fatigue, different FRP schemes and bonding systems, guided waves) where the data will take be presented in figures (.jpeg extension) with data from the records of deflections and reflections and transmissions (.xml files, .txt files), as well as photos (.png, .jpeg files) and videos (.mov extension).

Quality assurance of data

The PI will be responsible for quality assurance of the data from data collection, processing and data checking to data authenticity, and quality assurance of tests and simulation data.

The quality assurance of data will be achieved by following international guidelines and technical specifications on the experimental setups, measurements and calibration of equipment in each separate experimental procedure.

The quality assurance of data acquired in the simulations will be ensured by cross-checking with the agreement to the tested samples or the literature data.

Backup and security of data

The PI is aware that ensuring the collected primary data's safety is crucial to the research project. All data will be held on secure university servers at the University of Surrey, with a back-up held off-site at the University's second location. However, network security and security of computer systems and files to prevent unauthorised access or unwanted changes to data, disclosure or destruction of data will all be paid attention to in collaboration with the IT Department and the Centre for Cyber Security Centre of the University of Surrey. Data from planned activities and work off-campus will be securely stored in the university's secure cloud storage service.

Management and curation of data

The PI will collect data through: simulations, lab tests, industrial partners meetings. Simulation data will be stored by the input files and the post-processing of the results using special software (e.g. excel, matlab, grapher). Since the data collected from the lab tests will be in the form of records of deflections, displacements and frequency domain, but not formatted curves and figures, the PI will allow time for presenting the data data and keeping it stored safe and confidential. Sent data from the industrial partners will be stored safe and confidentially for further retrieval of data and processing. In this way the collected will be organised in directories containing folders with nested folders given names according to job executed/journal/conference, date and description. They will be well managed by a descriptive text README file inside each directory or added comments in the simulations files. The data will be also released in published papers in per-reviewed prestigious journals and conferences as per the schedule of the project. The University of Surrey has allocated the essential software for the research. The PI will be responsible for finding the technical support in the case of special needs.

Difficulties in data sharing and measures to overcome these

The large amount of data generated during the project will be communicated by online transfer platforms, hard copies and online safe repositories. The PI will be responsible for giving access to the data to the other researchers and partners. In agreement with the industrial partners of the project, as well as any governmental bodies involved (e.g. public stakeholders of bridges) data access will be given to: (a) legitimate researchers, (b) researchers under a restrictive licence or (c) researchers who consent to sign a non-disclosure agreement.

Consent, anonymisation and strategies to enable further re-use of data

The PI will make sure that the partners is well informed about the purpose and intended uses of the research, as well as what their participation in the research entails and what risks and benefits there are, if any. For further re-use of data, all the collected will be stored to well-known repositories such as Zenodo, for at least ten year's period defined at the MSCA Grant agreement and the European Union's policy on fully-funded research projects, as well as the Surrey Open Research policy. Consent matters doesn't apply to BriFace MSCA project since there won't be used any third-party data.

Copyright and intellectual property ownership

The PI will meet the copyright requirements for any potential innovations on the strengthening measures set down in the MSCA's Grant agreement and the Implementation Guide. The intellectual properties of the potential patents produced from the research during the project will be allocated according to the Intellectual Property Code of the University of Surrey upon agreement with the industrial partners. Additionally, it is understood that the MSCA will not accept liability for any complaint or legal action taken against a researcher or its data service providers for infringements of copyrights, defamation or any other data protection requirements.

Responsibilities

The PI will be responsible for data management of both simulations and lab tests and the management of data.